

Assessing Impact of Gamma Irradiation on Proximate Composition of White Yam, *Dioscorea Rotundata*: Pepa Specie Farmed in Nasarawa State

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Abstract

Previous attempts by Nigeria to export yams have not yielded the desired objectives because the yams were rejected due to rot, before reaching their destination. On the basis of the foregoing attempt was made to evaluate the impact of gamma irradiation on the proximate composition of the local Pepa yam, variety of the white yam; *Dioscorea Rotundata*. This was to determine the preservation ability of gamma radiation source and its durability. Pepa yam tubers were gathered from six Local Government Areas (LGA) of Nasarawa State using the judgmental sampling method. The irradiation was carried out using Co- 60 source at the Gamma Irradiation Facility of the Nigeria Atomic Energy Commission (NAEC), Abuja, F.C.T. The irradiation processing was done at varying dose rates with the dose limits ranging from 30Gy, 60Gy, 80Gy, 120Gy, 150Gy, 180Gy, 230Gy and 300Gy. The samples were stored for 5 months at ambient temperature in a room with floor covered with sand. The proximate compositions of the irradiated samples were analyzed using the standard methods of the Association of the Official Analytical Chemistry and resulting data processed with SPSS ANOVA using repeated measure t-test. This is to test for the measure of significance between values of the proximate composition immediately after irradiation (IAI) and five months after irradiation (A5M). Pearson Correlation was also performed to ascertain the relationships between the variables. Measured variables of the proximate compositions: crude ash, crude fat, crude protein, crude fibre, carbohydrate, revealed a statistically significant positive correlation $p < 0.01$ between the Pepa yam samples immediately after irradiation and 5 months later. This indicates that there is a relationship between the irradiation and the changes of the values of the proximate compositions and longevity in terms of the extended shelf-life of the Pepa yams.

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Keywords: Irradiation, Dormancy, Chemical residue, Degradation, Sprouting.

1. Introduction

There are about 600 yam species, among which six are economically important *Dioscorea Rotundata* and *Dioscorea Alata* are the most common species in Nigeria (James et al., 2012). Pepa yam is one of the local varieties of white yam that are indigenous to Nigeria and it is widely cultivated due to its taste, poundability in terms of smoothness of the yams and long shelf-life compared with other species. Nigeria is the largest producer of yams but attempts to enter into the global yam market was recently truncated with the rot of the yams and subsequent rejection by the destination countries (Chepkemoui, 2017; Ewepu, 2017). The situation can be adjudged to be due to the poor preservation mechanism that does not meet the standard of the importing countries.

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The two main causes of yam rot can be attributed to microbial infestation especially where there are bruises during transportation from the farm and sprouting due to translocation of nutrients (James et al., 2012). A matured yam after harvesting ordinarily stays from one - two months representing the dormancy period which is dependent on the temperature of storage, specie of yam, microbial infections, climate conditions during growth, harvest maturity and mechanical damage, among others (IAEA, 2002; Lawal et al., 2011). This period of yam dormancy ends with sprouting and it is evidenced by certain characteristics such as loss of weight, water content, carbohydrate content and other minerals due to translocation of these elements to the sprouts (Adesuyi, 1973). Degradation of yams commences with the depreciation in the proximate composition i.e. carbohydrate, ash, crude fibre, crude fat and protein. It then means that reducing the rate of the degradation will help to preserve the yams and improve its shelf life. Kooij (2012) asserts that inhibitory chemicals such as naphthalene, tetrachloronitrobenzene, acetic acid, maleic hydrazidylene have been used to delay sprouting and by implication yam degradation but the health implications due to chemical toxicity and residue has been an issue of concern. Food irradiation is one method that can be used to preserve the freshness of food and it presents an opportunity to extend the shelf-life of yams as well as its freshness by interfering in the physiological process (Waltar, 2003; IAEA, 2002).

Other sources of food irradiation exist as Kooij (2012) stated such as x-ray and electron beams but Moghadam et al. (2011), asserts that γ (gamma) rays is the most effective ionizing radiation for food irradiation. Therefore, this paper will focus on γ irradiation having been established that it is a more sustainable means of preserving yam (IAEA, 1997). Yams are of different varieties and researches have been carried out involving assessing the impact of γ irradiation on the local water yam, “Meccakusha” and “Obiaoturugo” yam species (Lawal et al., 2011; Nwachukwu, 2000) but none has been carried out on the Pepa yam specie. In the aforementioned studies, the dose limits have not been extended beyond 140Gy to explore the impact at this level despite of the resolutions by a competent body for food irradiation standards, the Codex Alimentarius Commission, establishing 10kGy as the maximum allowable value of food irradiation (IAEA, 2002). Therefore, this research will assess the impact of γ irradiation over a wide range of dose range applications beginning with 30Gy, 60Gy, 80Gy, 120Gy, 150Gy, 180Gy, 230Gy and 300Gy on the proximate composition of Pepa yam. This study will be useful to determine one of the topical issues that has affected the acceptability of irradiation as a means of food preservation (WHO, 1994). Resolving this problem will help the regulatory authorities especially in Nigeria to make appropriate standards for irradiated yams to boost revenues from export of Pepa yams.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

The materials used for the research include:

- i Pepa yam: The local specie of the white yam is Pepa yam and 45 freshly harvested tubers were obtained from farmers.
- ii Table Top Weighing Scale: It has the capacity to measure 1-10kg with accuracy of 99.9% using the Liquid Crystal Display (LCD).
- iii Cobalt 60 gamma source: The Gamma Irradiation Facility (GIF), the source of the γ irradiation used for the purposes of the irradiation is the γ radiation center operated by the Nigeria Atomic Energy Commission (NAEC) which is located at the Nuclear Technology Centre, Sheda, Abuja, FCT. The irradiation was done at the stationary mode at varying dose rate.
- iv Storage Area: The storage area consists of a room at 27 °C degrees Celsius with ground covered with sand. It has restricted access and large enough to contain 45 tubers of Pepa yam.

2.2. Methods

The local Pepa yam tubers were collected from six (6) Local Government Areas of Nasarawa State namely; Awe, Doma, Nasarawa Eggon, Lafia Central, Kokona and Keffi. A mixture of non-probability sampling methods such as the purposive/judgmental and accidental sampling were adopted in sampling the yams. This is because it is difficult

to establish an entire Pepa yam population in the domains. While some parts of the areas are inaccessible and certain physical characteristics of the yams like absence of decay or disease, severe bruises or wounds that might predispose the yams to decomposition are required for the experimentation. Using the identified sampling technique 45 tubers were collected from farmers around February period and kept for one week to get them ready for radiation processing using the Gamma Irradiation Facility of the Nigeria Atomic Energy Commission (NAEC). They were shared into nine (9) groups of five tubers each and subsequently marked for ease of identification. Eight (8) out of the 9 groups were treated with γ -radiation doses of 30Gy = A, 60Gy = B, 80Gy = C, 120Gy = D, 150Gy = E, 180Gy = F, 230Gy = G and 300Gy = H, while the ninth group served as the control/un-irradiated. The absorbed dose was measured incrementally (30Gy - 300Gy) using four (4) Bruker e-scan alanine dosimeters placed in the tote box as the yams were being irradiated by the Co 60 gamma source. Each dose range has five (5) tubers of Pepa yams to give the experiment a measure of validity and reliability. The processed yams were stored for five (5) months and evaluated for changes in their proximate composition. Before then, the initial conditions of the proximate composition of Pepa yams such as; carbohydrate content, protein, lipids and moisture content had been established. The proximate composition was carried out using the standard methods of the Association of the Official Analytical Chemistry (AOAC, 2005). The Protein content was analyzed by micro-kjeldhal method, moisture content was by oven drying method, crude lipid was by solvent method using soxhlet apparatus.

In terms of statistical techniques, both descriptive and inferential statistics were adopted in the study. The descriptive statistics were necessary to provide a descriptive explanation of the spread of the data as well as indicate the indexes (Norms) for interpreting the repeated measures of the yam. Repeated measure t-test was adopted to ascertain the difference between values of the proximate composition immediately after irradiation (IAI) and five months after irradiation (A5M) and also to ascertain the relationships between the variables.

3. Results

The irradiated Pepa yam tubers were analyzed to determine the impact of the dose treatments on the proximate composition over 5 months and the results are as follows:

Table 1. Proximate composition of Pepa yam before irradiation (un-irradiated/control sample).

Proximate Composition	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Before Irradiation	(%)		
Moisture	51.27	5	0.02
Ash	2.65	5	0.19
Crude fat	1.38	5	0.02
Crude protein	0.87	5	0.02
Crude fibre	1.54	5	0.02
Carbohydrate	68.34	5	0.02

Table 1 presents the mean proximate composition of the control Pepa yam samples before irradiation. The results show that a Pepa yam sample has an average concentration of carbohydrate = 68.3440%, moisture = 51.27% and trace quantities of fat = 1.38%, protein = 0.87%, fibre = 1.54% and ash = 2.65%.

Table 2 presents the proximate composition of the Pepa yam immediately after irradiation. Therefore, the difference in composition at various irradiation doses indicated that moisture content was increasing progressively across the samples from A - H as dose increases. The ash content increased with the initial samples A - F and started declining from G - H. The crude fat and proteins also increased across the samples from A - H as the dose increases. The fibre content increased progressively from sample A - D and started declining from sample E - H. The carbohydrate content was higher in A, maintained a steady decline and increased from G - H.

Table 2. Proximate composition immediately after irradiation.

Proximate composition immediately after irradiation		Sample A	Sample B	Sample C	Sample D	Sample E	Sample F	Sample G	Sample H
Moisture (%)	Mean	50.14	51.06	55.82	62.38	60.51	64.30	67.86	72.76
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	1.37	0.98	0.74	1.60	1.51	0.52	0.96	0.69
Ash (%)	Mean	1.52	1.74	1.76	1.85	1.67	1.63	1.54	1.49
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01
Crude fat (%)	Mean	1.24	1.35	2.05	2.23	2.14	2.14	2.57	2.66
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.04
Crude protein (%)	Mean	2.45	2.61	4.33	4.97	5.65	6.48	6.31	7.10
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	0.02	0.01	0.0219	0.22	0.20	0.02	0.02	0.03
Crude fibre (%)	Mean	0.56	1.06	1.48	1.74	1.35	1.12	0.59	0.82
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02
Carbohydrate (%)	Mean	48.58	46.20	46.38	44.83	46.20	46.04	50.83	51.28
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	1.98	1.45	1.33	2.12	1.29	1.80	4.85	1.98

Table 3 shows the proximate composition of the yam samples, five (5) months after irradiation. There is a fluctuation in the moisture content across the samples, indicating a steady increase from sample A = 48.71% to the highest value at sample D = 57.26%. It declines at sample E = 49.66%, increases again at sample F = 55.35% and declines steadily at sample H = 51.46%. The Ash content indicated a fluctuation along the samples from sample A = 1.84% and ending at sample H = 1.72%. Both crude fat and protein witnessed a steady rise in content from sample A to H as the dose increases. The crude fibre increased progressively from samples A = 0.89% to D = 2.04% started declining in content until sample H at 0.92%. The carbohydrate increased from sample A = 56.46% with slight fluctuations along the samples, having the highest value at sample C = 58.95% till 56.79% at sample H as the dose increases. The emphasis is to compare the proximate composition of the irradiated yam samples and the un-irradiated as represented in Table 1. The variations among the samples on the proximate composition is an indication of an effect on the content.

Table 4 shows that the result of the repeated measure t-test revealed a statistically significant difference across the six composition where moisture content indicated $t(8) = 3.265$, $P < 0.01$, Ash content $t(8) = -6.256$, $P < 0.01$, Crude fat content $t(8) = -2.976$, $P < 0.01$, Crude protein $t(8) = -6.975$, $P < 0.01$, Crude fibre content $t(8) = 4.953$, $P < 0.01$ and Carbohydrate content $t(8) = 6.102$, $P < 0.01$. This results shows that the applied doses interacted differently with the proximate composition across the samples in the long run.

Table 5 shows the relationship between proximate composition immediately after irradiation and five months after irradiation across the six composition where the result revealed a statistically significant positive correlation at the for; pair2 $r(8) = 0.991$, $P < 0.01$; pair3 $r(8) = 0.997$, $P < 0.01$; pair4 $r(8) = 0.999$, $P < 0.01$; pair5 $r(8) = 0.927$, $P < 0.01$; and pair6 $r(8) = 0.884$, $P < 0.01$, respectively. But no statistical significant relationship between pair1 $r(8) = 0.455$, $P > 0.01$. This implies that ash, crude fat, crude protein, crude fibre and carbohydrate maintained their composition

Table 3. Proximate composition five (5) months after irradiation.

Proximate composition immediately after irradiation		Sample A	Sample B	Sample C	Sample D	Sample E	Sample F	Sample G	Sample H
Moisture (%)	Mean	48.71	45.79	54.47	57.26	49.66	55.35	52.12	51.46
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	1.54	1.35	1.78	1.27	1.28	3.65	1.49	0.75
Ash (%)	Mean	1.84	1.90	1.98	1.98	1.84	1.82	1.76	1.72
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01
Crude fat (%)	Mean	1.28	1.39	2.10	2.36	2.11	2.69	2.61	2.74
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.41	0.08	0.31	0.14	0.31
Crude protein (%)	Mean	2.83	2.96	4.58	5.25	5.86	6.71	6.64	7.41
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	0.03	0.01	0.13	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03
Crude fibre (%)	Mean	0.89	1.16	1.82	2.04	1.73	1.46	1.08	0.92
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
Carbohydrate (%)	Mean	56.46	57.91	58.95	57.55	58.65	57.40	56.96	56.79
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Std. Deviation	1.96	1.85	1.81	0.42	0.04	0.04	0.08	0.09

Table 4. Comparing the difference in the proximate composition immediately after irradiation and five months later.

		No of Samples	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	p-value
Pair 1	Moisture IAI	9	59.54	8.00	8	3.265	0.011
	Moisture A5M	9	51.79	3.54			
Pair 2	Ash IAI	9	1.76	0.35	8	-6.256	0.000
	Ash A5M	9	1.94	0.28			
Pair 3	Crude fat IAI	9	2.01	0.55	8	-2.976	0.018
	Crude fat A5M	9	2.06	0.57			
Pair 4	Crude protein IAI	9	4.53	2.13	8	-6.975	0.000
	Crude protein A5M	9	4.79	2.18			
Pair 5	Crude fibre IAI	9	1.40	0.41	8	4.953	0.001
	Crude fibre A5M	9	1.14	0.42			
Pair 6	Carbohydrate IAI	9	58.78	3.68	8	6.102	0.000
	Carbohydrate A5M	9	49.85	7.29			

significantly and relatively except moisture content after repeated measure. In other words, radiation does not change

the nature, composition and taste of the Pepa yam.

Table 5. Comparing the difference in the proximate composition immediately after irradiation and five months later.

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Moisture IAI & Moisture A5M	9	.455	.218
Pair 2	Ash IAI & Ash A5M	9	.991	.000
Pair 3	Crude fat IAI & Crude fat A5M	9	.997	.000
Pair 4	Crude protein IAI & Crude protein A5M	9	.999	.000
Pair 5	Crude fibre IAI & Crude fibre A5M	9	.927	.000
Pair 6	Carbohydrate IAI & Carbohydrate A5M	9	.884	.002

4. Discussions

The results of the irradiation of Pepa yam samples within the dose limits of 30Gy - 300Gy representing A - H with varying intervals of 30Gy and 50Gy to determine the impact on proximate composition are presented and discussed under the following variables:

- i Moisture: The analysis of the proximate composition of the Pepa yam immediately after irradiation indicates that the moisture content increased progressively across the samples above the 51.27 threshold of the control sample. After 5 months of storage, the moisture content decreased in samples A and B, increased around samples C and D, decreased again at sample E and G and started improving towards the control values. This nature of interaction does not show a linear relationship between moisture retention and dose increment but it is evident that at 300Gy, one can obtain a near quality as the control in terms of moisture content. This is affirmed in Table 5 on paired sample correlations between the proximate compositions immediately after irradiation and 5 months later, where no statistical significant relationship and moderate correlation was established at Pair1 $r(8) = 0.455$, $P > 0.01$. In a similar research for Meccakusha white yam variety, the moisture content were significantly greater than the control (Lawal et al., 2011), it was seen that radiation retains moisture content of yam at storage (James et al., 2012).
- ii Ash: The ash content were observed to have reduced immediately after irradiation across the samples as the dose increased but it was not a linear relationship. It reached its peak at sample D = 1.8480 with its lowest at sample H = 1.4920. However in 5months, the ash content increased across the samples though not linearly, the highest being sample D = 1.978 and the least being sample H = 1.7180. Lawal et al. (2011) opined that ash associated with mineral content remained unaffected by radiation as it was significantly higher in irradiated Meccakusha yam tubers than the control. The ash content in the irradiated Pepa yam tubers are lower than the control samples within the dose range of this experiment. In the least, sample H is lower than control by 35% while the highest point sample D is lower than the control by 25.5%. However, the relationship between ash content immediately and after five months irradiation revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between pair2 $r(8) = 0.991$, $P < 0.01$. This means that the ash content maintained their composition significantly and relatively. This shows that irradiation does not affect the mineral content of yam tubers (James et al., 2012).
- iii Crude Fat: The crude fat increased progressively from sample A - H immediately after irradiation with the least sample A = 1.2380 and highest sample H = 2.6560. This is higher than the control 1.3760. At 5 months, the crude fat increased from the previous values across the samples though not linearly, the least being sample A = 1.2820 and highest H = 2.7420. Table 5 shows the relationship between crude fat composition immediately after irradiation and five months after where the result revealed a statistically significant positive correlation pair3 $r(8) = 0.997$, $P < 0.01$. This also shows that crude fat maintained its composition significantly and relatively. Compared with water yam, it is observed that the crude fat contents for both species were somewhat higher in irradiated tubers than the control (James et al., 2012). This was also the case for the Meccakusha species (Lawal et al., 2011).

- iv Crude Protein: The mean crude protein were increasing across the samples as dose increases immediately after irradiation, the highest rate was recorded at H = 7.1040. After 5months of irradiation, the protein were found to have also increased across the samples with H recording the highest value at 7.4100. Table 5 indicates the relationship between crude protein immediately after irradiation and five months after where the result revealed a statistically significant positive correlation at pair4 $r(8) = 0.999$, $P < 0.01$, which implies that the protein content maintained their composition significantly and relatively after repeated measure. The increased crude protein value for the irradiated yam against the control would imply that irradiated Pepa yam tubers have improved protein content. Protein content in the irradiated yams were observed to be higher compared with the control for the water yam as well as the Meccakusha yams respectively (James et al., 2012; Lawal et al., 2011).
- v Crude Fibre: Immediately after irradiation, it was discovered that the mean crude protein content was increasing from sample A = 0.5640 and recorded the highest value at sample D = 1.7420. In 5 months, it further increased but not linearly from sample A = 0.8940 to D = 2.0400 which is the highest point from which it starts depreciating to 0.9240 at sample H. Table 5 indicates the relationship between crude fibre immediately after irradiation and five months revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between pair5 $r(8) = 0.927$, $P < 0.01$, implying that the crude content maintained their composition significantly and relatively after repeated measure. The crude fibre content did not show any appreciable change in its composition in 21weeks after irradiation in the case of Meccakusha and seven months for water yam (Lawal et al., 2011; James et al., 2012).
- vi Carbohydrate: The carbohydrate content was observed to have decreased across the samples from A = 48.5800 picked up from sample G = 50.8340 and reaching its maximum value at sample H = 51.2780. At the end of 5 months, the mean value of the carbohydrate increased across the samples but it was not linear. Sample A = 56.4640 was among the least values, sample C = 58.9540 recorded the highest value while sample H = 56.7860. All samples were below the control = 68.3440. Table 5 indicates the relationship between carbohydrate immediately after irradiation and five months later revealed a statistically significant positive correlation between pair5 $r(8) = 0.927$, $P < 0.01$, implying that the carbohydrate content maintained their composition significantly and relatively after repeated measure. This is the same for the other study with no significant difference observed in the carbohydrate content both for the control and irradiated yams (Lawal et al., 2011).
- vii Dose: Essentially, the yams have different characteristics represented by the mass, volume shape/contour of the yams, so that the radiation will interact differently with different masses. Also, where the sample spends more time within the vicinity of the source, it is likely to absorb more than the sample that spends little time. This is the same with the sample that is very close to the source. The impact of the irradiation treatment on the proximate composition of the Pepa yams did not show a linear relationship between the dose and the composition. This is further seen in Table 5 where there is statistical significant difference across the six proximate composition within the 5 months period after repeated measure t-test. Comparing the proximate compositions of the control sample (Table 1) and five months after irradiation (Table 3) shows that radiation treatment maintains or preserves the quality of yam particularly within the region of G - H dose levels.

5. Conclusion

The study clearly shows that at 300Gy represented by sample H, it is possible to obtain as near original quality of Pepa yam. All measured variables of the proximate compositions, crude ash, crude fat, crude protein, crude fibre, carbohydrate revealed a statistically significant correlation between the Pepa yams immediately after irradiation and 5months later. Thus, showing that there is a relationship between the irradiation and the changes of the values of the proximate compositions and longevity in terms of the extended shelf-life of the Pepa yams. This research shows an interesting feature about food irradiation, that it can preserve the freshness of food. Farmers in Nigeria can leverage on this technique to ensure a long term food availability of Pepa yams and also make the most from its exportation to improve their living standards as well as earning foreign exchange for Nigeria.

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